
Structured Decision Making for Aquatic Systems Management and Wildlife-Hazard Reduction at DTW

Wayne County Airport Authority
Airfield Operations Department, Wildlife Division
Special Publication No. 25-04

Last Revision:

31 December 2025

Purpose:

To evaluate pond- and fish-management strategies for DTW and provide a recommendation using a structured decision-making approach

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Suggested citation:

Gurney, S., and S. Creed. 2025. Structured decision making for aquatic systems management and wildlife-hazard reduction at DTW. Special Publication No. 25-04. Wayne County Airport Authority, Airfield Operations Department–Wildlife Division, Detroit, MI, USA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18110594>.

Above, photographs from DTW illustrating fish–wildlife interactions and associated aviation risks, including double-crested cormorants concentrating and foraging in retention ponds; goldfish recovered from cormorant digestive tracts; a documented cormorant–aircraft wing strike; natural goldfish winterkill events (2016–2025); gull ingestion by an aircraft engine; osprey predation on goldfish; mature goldfish exceeding 1 ft in length; and invasive snails.

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Preface

Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) is committed to maintaining the highest standards of aviation safety, security, and operational efficiency. In alignment with 14 CFR § 139.337 and DTW's Wildlife Hazard Management Plan, the identification and mitigation of wildlife hazards are essential to reducing wildlife-aircraft strike risk and protecting airfield operations and the traveling public. Invasive goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) have emerged as a persistent hazard at DTW, serving as a food source for fish-eating birds that pose elevated risk to aircraft safety.

To address this challenge, the Wayne County Airport Authority (WCAA) Airfield Operations Department–Wildlife Division conducted a systematic evaluation of goldfish populations and pond conditions at DTW, applying a structured decision-making framework to develop transparent, defensible, and operationally feasible pond and fish management strategies. This work was completed in partnership with the WCAA Environmental Department through the DTW Pond and Fish Management Working Group, integrating expertise in wildlife ecology, fisheries biology, water quality, stormwater engineering, chemistry, and environmental compliance.

The project also benefited from advising and technical input from local, state, and federal organizations, representing strong cross-agency coordination. External partners included the Michigan Department of Natural Resources (MDNR) Fisheries Division and Aquatic Invasive Species Program; the Michigan Department of Environment, Great Lakes, and Energy (EGLE); the U.S. Department of Agriculture–Wildlife Services; the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service; Idaho Department of Fish and Game; Greater Orlando Aviation Authority; Crown Castle; GEI Consultants; Environmental Consulting and Technology; and the Great Lakes Environmental Center. These partners contributed expertise in fish ecology, invasive-species management, permitting, and regulatory compliance.

The findings and recommendations in this report build upon earlier guidance developed by WCAA biologists and USDA–Wildlife Services, formalizing those concepts into a comprehensive, science-based strategy supported by quantitative analysis and expert review. This work reinforces DTW's commitment to collaborative, data-driven, and adaptive wildlife-hazard management and contributes to the WCAA Wildlife Division's Special Publication Series, which is intended to preserve institutional knowledge, support transparent decision-making, and provide a resource for other airports facing similar challenges.

Executive Summary

- **Rotenone was identified as the most effective near-term solution.** It consistently outperformed all other options in our structured decision-making analysis—roughly 2–3 times more effective than common mechanical methods—while also reducing wildlife-hazard risk and treatment frequency.
- **Basin renovation and drying is the best long-term solution when feasible.** Converting ponds to drainable or underground systems would prevent long-term fish persistence, but high costs and multi-year construction timelines make near-term implementation unlikely.
- **Mechanical removal methods are not enough.** Netting, electrofishing, and similar approaches scored only ~38–55% as effective as rotenone and are unlikely to achieve lasting reduction in fish abundance or wildlife-hazard risk.
- **Goldfish increase both wildlife-hazard risk and water-quality impacts.** They attract hazardous fish-eating birds and stir up sediments, reducing stormwater-pond performance—the opposite of DTW’s hazard management and water-quality goals.
- **Regulators support rotenone use at DTW.** EGLE and MDNR indicated that rotenone is permissible and appropriate given the aviation-safety risk posed by fish-eating birds.
- **DTW’s fish problem has likely gone unmanaged for more than a decade.** Multiple contractor proposals were advanced previously, but no consensus was reached until this structured-decision process aligned objectives and stakeholder values.
- **Recolonization will occur naturally over time—monitoring is essential.** Even highly effective treatments may require future maintenance actions, reinforcing the need for adaptive management.
- **The structured decision-making process made our recommendation transparent, defensible, and collaborative.** It clearly linked objectives, alternatives, and consequences so leadership can see why the recommended option is best.

Introduction

Decision making is central to natural-resource management, yet managers are routinely asked to make choices under conditions of uncertainty, competing objectives, operational constraints, and diverse stakeholder values. These challenges are not unique to wildlife management; humans generally struggle with complex choices involving multiple objectives and uncertain outcomes (Runge 2011). Indeed, management decision making has been recognized as the core work of wildlife professionals, who must integrate ecological, social, economic, and political considerations to produce valued outcomes (Fuller et al. 2020). Structured decision making provides a systematic, transparent framework for addressing such challenges by explicitly linking management objectives, alternative actions, and expected consequences (Runge 2011, Gregory et al. 2012; Figure 1).

Rooted in decision science and risk analysis, structured decision making emphasizes the use of the best available science, explicit treatment of uncertainty, and clear articulation of trade-offs, while also incorporating organizational and societal values into the decision process. The process emphasizes collaboration, inclusiveness, and clarity—helping diverse stakeholders develop a shared understanding of what matters, how actions are expected to perform, and where uncertainty may limit confidence in predicted outcomes. When revisited through time and supported by monitoring and learning, structured decision making provides the conceptual foundation for adaptive management. Increasingly, systematic decision-science frameworks are recognized as essential tools for improving conservation outcomes while supporting accountability, defensibility, and communication among managers, stakeholders, and decision makers (Fuller et al. 2020).

Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) faces a persistent wildlife-hazard concern associated with invasive goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) in stormwater retention ponds. These fish create concentrated forage for fish-eating birds, including several species identified as among the most hazardous to aviation safety at DTW (Gurney et al. 2025) and species strongly associated with damaging wildlife–aircraft strikes nationwide, such as double-crested cormorants (*Nannopterum auritum*), gulls (*Larus spp.*), osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*), and bald eagles (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*; DeVault et al. 2011, Ross et al. 2025). Importantly, damaging-strike rates at DTW have been higher than average over the past three years, with fish-eating birds representing a major contributing factor. In addition to increasing wildlife–aircraft strike risk, sediment-suspending fishes like goldfish—which are highly tolerant of extreme environmental conditions—can also worsen water quality by increasing turbidity and nutrient recycling, the opposite of what is desired

in a stormwater-management system (Prejs et al. 1997; Eilers et al. 2011). Multiple pond- and fish-management strategies have been proposed—including mechanical removal, basin drying, and chemical control—but their relative effectiveness, feasibility, and risk implications remain uncertain. Although the goldfish problem at DTW has likely persisted for over a decade and numerous contractor proposals were forwarded to senior management during that period, the absence of consensus among WCAA staff meant that the issue remained unmanaged—highlighting the need for a structured decision process. In recognition of the growing hazard, the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup was established to develop a coordinated, strategy to reduce fish abundance in stormwater ponds—thereby decreasing their attractiveness to hazardous bird species while also improving pond function and water quality.

Our goal with this study was to apply a structured decision-making framework to identify the management alternative that best reduces goldfish abundance and associated wildlife hazards while remaining operationally feasible and compliant with regulatory requirements. Our objectives were to (1) define the decision context and management objectives, (2) develop a suite of feasible pond- and fish-management alternatives, (3) estimate the expected consequences of each alternative relative to these objectives, and (4) identify the highest-utility management action. Although implementation, monitoring, and continual learning fall beyond the scope of this paper, we emphasize their importance as the final step in completing the structured decision-making cycle. By applying structured decision making in partnership with the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup, we aim to provide a transparent, repeatable decision process that integrates biological knowledge, regulatory considerations, and operational reality to guide long-term fish and wildlife hazard management at a major commercial airport.

Figure 1. Overview of the structured decision-making framework, adapted from Gregory et al. (2012). The process begins by defining the decision context, after which a series of structuring steps guide the evaluation of alternatives and the eventual selection and implementation of a preferred management action. The “refine” loop indicates that insights gained at any stage can be used to revisit and improve earlier steps.

Methods

Decision context

Problem statement, goal, and timeframe

The problem statement addressed in this study was that overabundant goldfish in retention ponds at DTW attract fish-eating birds that are hazardous and disruptive to aircraft operations. The goal to be achieved by implementing management action was to reduce fish abundance in ponds in order to decrease pond attractiveness to fish-eating birds and thereby reduce presence of wildlife hazards to aviation. The timeframe for the decision problem was five years (2025–2030), which we considered more palatable than longer planning horizons and better aligned with operational and budgeting cycles at DTW.

Spatial extent and constraints

The location and spatial extent of the decision problem included two primary source retention ponds supporting fish populations (Pond 3E and Pond 3W), while also considering the potential for Pond 4 to function as a reservoir capable of reintroducing fish to primary ponds. We identified several important constraints influencing the decision, including budget limitations, the continued need for stormwater storage and discharge to the public side, limitations on water-level manipulation and site accessibility (e.g., mucky substrate), and the requirement to operate within existing permits or what is reasonably permissible.

The timing of work was another critical constraint, especially to the Environmental Department. Water-level manipulation and discharge activities were considered most feasible during summer and early fall (approximately 01 June–01 October), when permitting requirements are less restrictive and de-icing agents are absent from the stormwater system. Additional constraints include restrictions on the types of chemicals that may be introduced to stormwater ponds (e.g., piscicides, neutralizing agents) and limits on biochemical oxygen demand and other water-quality constituents.

Decision makers

In response to the problem statement, we established the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup, consisting of staff from the Wayne County Airport Authority (WCAA) Airfield Operations Department – Wildlife Division and Environmental Department. We applied the structured decision-making process through regularly scheduled Workgroup meetings to identify feasible management alternatives and evaluate their relative performance. Management actions considered included standard fish

management techniques and combinations thereof. The Workgroup was tasked with identifying and evaluating management alternatives and developing a recommended course of action. Workgroup members would be responsible for planning on-the-ground implementation and oversight if approved, whereas WCAA senior leadership's (Vice President – Operations and Maintenance; Director – Environment & Sustainability; Senior Vice President/Chief Financial Officer) role was to review the recommendation and determine whether to authorize and fund the project.

Decision criteria (objectives)

We defined decision criteria, also referred to as objectives in structured decision making, to reflect the values and priorities relevant to pond and fish management and wildlife hazard reduction at DTW. Consistent with decision-analysis best practices, objectives were developed to be complete, concise, specific, and value-focused, ensuring that all key considerations influencing the decision were explicitly represented—and importantly, articulated before alternatives were formally generated (Keeney 1992; Gregory et al. 2012). Decision criteria were tailored to the decision context and five-year planning horizon and were intended to capture both operational and risk-related considerations relevant to airport management. Objectives addressed economic efficiency, biological effectiveness, timeliness of outcomes, feasibility of implementation, liability and regulatory risk, and the attractiveness of ponds to hazardous wildlife (Table 1). Each objective was further defined by one or more components describing the underlying factors contributing to performance and was paired with a measurable attribute to support comparative evaluation of management alternatives (Table 1). Decision criteria, along with their components and associated measurable attributes, were collaboratively identified during DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup sessions.

Table 1. The decision criteria, or objectives, its components, and the associated measurables for each. These criteria were used to help rank our management alternatives for the fish-management program at DTW (relative to the five-year decision timeframe).

Decision criteria (objectives)	Components included	Measurable attribute
Minimize 5-year cost	Planning and coordination, implementation	Dollar amount
Maximize effectiveness	Fish removed	Proportion of fish population
Minimize treatment frequency needed to reduce fish population	Treatment frequency	Years
Minimize 5-year implementation difficulty	Frequency of treatments, hours of effort, number of WCAA staff required, logistics, permitting	Time (e.g., hours, days, years)
Minimize 5-year liability	Regulatory compliance, wildlife-aircraft collisions	Risk of violations, strike metrics, wildlife presence
Minimize 5-year attractiveness to hazardous wildlife	Hazardous wildlife present at the ponds and adjacent areas	Wildlife counts, wildlife presence

Management alternatives

The DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup identified a set of feasible management alternatives for evaluation. The team then documented the advantages and limitations of each alternative using information from scientific literature, agency reports, best management practices, and standard operating procedures. These assessments were supplemented by structured expert elicitation with WCAA staff and multi-agency, interdisciplinary advisors (Table 2). Together, this process ensured that each alternative reflected both scientific evidence and operational feasibility at DTW.

Table 2. Advantages and limitations of each fish-management alternative evaluated for the DTW fish-management program. Information was synthesized from scientific literature (e.g., peer-reviewed publications, agency reports) and internal and external expert elicitation. References are cited as superscripts and described in the footer.

Management alternative	Advantages	Limitations
Status quo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy, no effort required • Low initial cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmanaged problem • Misaligned with WCAA goals, like safety and sustainability²⁵ • Potential for negligence claims and subsequent liability²⁵ • Unmanaged problem may have high costs associated with it later²⁵
Chemical treatment: rotenone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can eradicate entire fish populations^{1,2,4,5,6,8,9,11,12,13,17,18,20,22,26} • Likely requires a single treatment in a 5 or 10-year period⁴ • Goldfish eradication can help improve water quality^{6,7} • Will require additional permitting for stormwater chemical additive²⁵ • After year one, permitting will be relatively easy² • Breaks down faster in scummy waters⁴ • Rain events can help dilute and reduce toxicity²⁵ • Simple math for calculating concentrations²⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather dependent application² • Highly regulated process² • First year heavy with permitting² • Potential for a surge in attractants over multiple days (floating, euthanized fish)⁴ • May not be a palatable option for some individuals, given the visuals^{2,19} • Stormwater holding and discharge limitations²⁵

Chemical treatment: carbon dioxide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It can be applied in winter when stormwater discharge is limited, so it can sit a while and break down¹ • Larval fish may be more sensitive¹ • Can enhance natural winter mortality² • May also help address DTW invasive snail problem¹ • Simple testing of after quality post treatment, pH just must meet standards² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works best under ice^{1,2,23} • Ice conditions may limit effectiveness²³ • Variable effectiveness among species, including species tolerant to pollution^{1,23} • Introducing a chemical during critical breakdown period for de-icing agents²⁵ • Snail removal may require feverishly removing them from shore¹ • Will require additional permitting for stormwater chemical additive²⁵ • Accessibility challenges in winter²⁵ • Dead fish may freeze in ice and serve as continuous attractant²⁵ • Need for aerators to distribute treatment²³
Mechanical harvest: seining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to get many fish in a single pass with net⁹ • Simply add amendment to current Scientific Collector's Permit¹ • Relatively acceptable by public⁵ • Potential to target aggregations of fish^{15,16,21} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely to eradicate fish population^{1,4,5} • Relatively high effort^{4,8,9,14} • Requires annual treatments^{4,14} • Limited effectiveness for fish along shore and in shallows⁹ • Difficult implementation if there are obstructions⁹ • Accessibility challenges for larger boats⁹ • May be biased towards some classes of fish^{1,23}
Mechanical harvest: electrofishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May help reduce fish abundance if applied annually¹¹ • Good team building within and across departments³ • Could get the equipment and do it all with internal staff³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely to eradicate fish population^{4,5,8} • Relatively high effort^{4,8,9,11,14} • Requires annual treatments^{3,4,8,11,14} • Limit effectiveness for fish in deep water^{1,3,4} • Potential boat accessibility challenges^{9,25} • May be biased towards some classes of fish¹

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for shallow waters¹ • Simply add amendment to current Scientific Collector's Permit¹ • Relatively acceptable by the public⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has performed poorly to deter fish-eating birds at airports, like eagles and osprey³
<p>Mechanical harvest: combination of seining, electrofishing, and passive trapping</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximize effectiveness by combining mechanical efforts, including active and passive approaches^{9,11} • Electrofishing can target fish in the shallows and cover, whereas seining can target fish in deeper open area⁹ • Simply add amendment to current Scientific Collector's Permit¹ • Relatively acceptable by public⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely to eradicate fish population^{4,5,8} • Logistically complex⁹ • Relatively high effort^{8,9,14} • Requires annual treatments^{8,14} • May need multiple water levels by treatment type (e.g., seining boat accessibility versus electrofishing boat)⁹
<p>Mechanical harvest: systematic corralling (unified or unified-modified method)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to remove large proportion of fish²³ • Potential to work at desired pace, as ponds are worked sections at a time²³ • Simply add amendment to current Scientific Collector's Permit¹ • Relatively acceptable by public⁵ • Potential to target aggregations of fish^{15,16,21} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely to eradicate fish population^{4,5,8} • Logistically complex^{8,9} • Relatively high effort^{8,9,14} • May take days or weeks to implement • Requires annual treatments⁸ • Heavy rain may impact effectiveness (e.g., fish escaping corrals)²⁵ • May be biased towards some classes of fish^{1,23} • Potential for surges in attractants (corralled fish)²⁵
<p>Basin manipulation: drain ponds dry (no renovation)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered a best management practice^{1,8,24} • No additional permitting²⁵ • Addresses root cause of fish problem • Relatively low cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water remains in pools, so the effectiveness may be limited⁵ • May be difficult to manage stormwater during basin drying²⁵

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for surges in attractants (dead fish or fish trapped in areas unable to completely drain)²⁵ • Fish cleanup costs and accessibility challenges given mucky substrate²⁵ • May take a month or two for larval stage of fish to dry out¹ • Environmentally disruptive⁵ • Concerns with other species, like turtles¹⁰ • Potential worker safety concerns with mucky conditions; and snapping turtles⁹
<p>Basin manipulation: drain ponds dry (major renovation)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert consensus as the best management practice^{1,8,24} • Addresses root cause of fish problem • Addresses unique problem with DTW retention ponds²⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very expensive^{1,25} • Big undertaking^{1,25} • May be difficult to manage stormwater during basin manipulation²⁵ • Water remains in pools, so the effectiveness may be limited⁵ • May take a month or two for larval stage of fish to dry out¹ • Environmentally disruptive⁵ • Concerns with other species, like turtles¹⁰
<p>Biological control: predator stocking (e.g., largemouth bass, northern pike)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often viewed as a more natural or organic approach²⁵ • Relatively low cost⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited success and unpredictable results⁵ • May take a few years to affect prey population²⁵ • Adding fish to a system where fish are undesirable²⁵ • Larger fish may be attractive to larger, more hazardous avian predators²⁵

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- Poor water quality associated with ponds may limit the survival of some introduced species²⁵
 - Concerns with pathogens and legal requirements⁵
 - Permit limits on what species are allowed (likely based on local fish community)²⁵
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¹Personal communication, Justin Bopp (Invasive Species Program Coordinator), Michigan Department of Natural Resources–Invasive Species Program

²Personal communication. Darrin McCullough (Aquatic Biologist, Water Quality and Aquatic Nuisance Control Permits Unit), Michigan Department of Environment, Great Lakes, and Energy

³Personal communication, Rachael Wickliffe (Wildlife Management Specialist), at Greater Orlando Aviation Authority

⁴Personal communication, Nate Tilloston (Regional Fisheries Biologist specialized in invasive fish management), Idaho Department of Fish and Game

⁵ Finlayson et al. 2018

⁶Prejs et al. 1997

⁷Eilers et al. 2011

⁸Personal communication, John Buszkiewicz (Fisheries Management Biologist, Lake Erie Management Unit) and Cleyo Harris (Fisheries Biologist, Lake Erie Management Unit), Michigan Department of Natural Resources–Fisheries Division

⁹Personal communication, Ryan Holem (Senior Professional), GEI Consultants, Inc.

¹⁰Personal communication, Melissa Nichols (Aquatic Species Program Human Dimensions Analyst), Michigan Department of Natural Resources–Invasive Species Program

¹¹Rytwinski et al. 2019

¹²Sandodden et al. 2022

¹³Sandodden et al. 2018

¹⁴Yick et al. 2021

¹⁵Boston et al. 2024

¹⁶Bajer et al. 2011

¹⁷Britton and Brazier 2006

¹⁸Massengill 2014

¹⁹McClay 2000

²⁰Massengill 2022

²¹Penne and Pierce 2008

²²Olaf et al. 2014

²³Cupp et al. 2021

²⁴Loppnow 2022

²⁵DTW Pond and Fish Working Group, WCAA Airfield Operations Department – Wildlife Division and Environmental Department

²⁶Personal communication, Dennis McCauley (President/Senior Environmental Scientist), GLEC

Estimating consequences

As an early step in the structured decision-making process, we developed a consequence table to summarize the expected performance of each management alternative relative to the decision objectives (Table 3). Performance expectations were informed by each option's documented advantages and limitations (Table 2) and by cost estimates derived through contracting services. Because performance metrics varied substantially in scale and type, some consequences were expressed in relative rather than absolute terms to support direct comparison across objectives. We also incorporated quantitative fields where available (e.g., cost and implementation time), while other objectives without precise numerical estimates relied on semi-quantitative descriptors that capture outcomes relevant to aviation safety and risk management.

Table 3. Consequence table summarizing expected performance for each management alternative for the DTW fish-management program over a five-year planning horizon. Performance estimates reflect the best available information, including cost projections, documented advantages and limitations, and expert elicitation.

Management alternative	5-year cost (\$)	Effectiveness	Treatment frequency	5-year difficulty	5-year liability	5-year attractiveness to hazardous wildlife
Status quo	0	Low	5	Low	High	High
Chemical treatment: rotenone	50,000 ^a	High	1	Medium	Low	Low
Chemical treatment: carbon dioxide	50,000 ^b	Medium	2	Medium	Medium	Low
Mechanical harvest: seining	250,000 ^c	Medium	5	Medium	Medium	Medium
Mechanical harvest: electrofishing	250,000 ^c	Medium	5	Medium	Medium	Medium
Mechanical harvest: combination of seining, electrofishing, and passive trapping	300,000 ^c	Medium	5	High	Medium	Medium

Mechanical harvest: systematic corralling (unified or unified- modified method)	275,000 ^c	Medium	5	High	Medium	High
Basin manipulation: drain ponds dry (no renovation)	5,500 ^f	High	2	High	Medium	Medium
Basin manipulation: drain ponds dry (major renovation)	1,000,000 ^d	High	1	High	Low	Low
Biological control: predator stocking (e.g., largemouth bass, northern pike)	20,000 ^e	Low	2	Low	High	High

^aEnvironmental Consulting & Technology, Inc. (ECT; estimate retrieved 21 Jul 2023)

^bCost assumed equivalent to other chemical treatment (rotenone)

^cGEI Consultants, Inc. (estimate retrieved 11 Apr 2025)

^dCost assumed to be a minimum of \$1,000,000

^eCost assumed to be \$5.00 per 6–8” largemouth bass (approximate industry median) and a standard stocking rate of 100 fish per acre for two ponds approximating 20 acres

^fClean-up cost assumed to approximate ECT’s disposal and 3-day labor cost.

Ranking alternatives

Relative rankings

We derived relative rankings directly from the advantages-and-limitations and consequence tables (Tables 2 and 3) to translate qualitative and semi-quantitative performance information into ordinal ranks suitable for quantitative analysis. For each decision criterion (objective), we ranked management alternatives from 1 (best) to N (worst), where N represented the total number of alternatives considered (Table 4). Because some alternatives performed equally on certain criteria (e.g., comparable cost estimates), we allowed ties to avoid assigning artificial differences between alternatives. When options were indistinguishable within the resolution of available information—whether due to uncertainty or true equivalency—we assigned them the same rank. When ties prevented a complete 1-to-N ranking sequence, we placed alternatives on a general ordinal scale to reflect their relative performance (Table 4).

We assigned lower ranks to alternatives that performed more desirably relative to the decision objectives, whereas alternatives expected to perform poorly received higher ranks. Overall, this relative-ranking step provided us with a standardized, dimensionless representation of relative performance across criteria, enabling subsequent normalization and calculation of utility scores. By grounding rankings directly in the advantages-and-limitations and consequence tables (Tables 2 and 3), we maintained transparency and traceability between qualitative assessments and quantitative decision outputs.

Table 4. Relative rankings of management alternatives for the DTW fish-management program over a five-year timeframe. Alternatives were ranked by decision criteria (objectives), with lower ranks assigned to options that performed more desirably relative to the objectives and higher ranks indicating poorer performance. Ranking objectives included maximizing the effectiveness of fish removal and minimizing cost, implementation time (or treatment frequency), implementation difficulty, liability, and attractiveness to wildlife hazardous to aircraft operation.

Alternative	Cost	Effectiveness	Frequency	Difficulty	Liability	Attractiveness
Status quo	1	8	6	1	8	10
Rotenone	4	2	1	3	1	1
CO ₂	4	4	2	4	4	2
Seining	5	6	6	5	6	6
Electrofishing	5	6	6	5	6	5
Mechanical combo	7	5	6	6	5	7
Corralling	6	5	6	6	5	8
Dry out basin	2	3	5	7	3	4
Renovate and dry	8	1	4	8	2	3
Predator stocking	3	7	3	2	7	9

Normalized rankings

To enable quantitative comparison of management alternatives across multiple decision criteria, we transformed relative rankings into normalized utility values (Table 5). This was an important step because normalization converts ranks assigned on different criteria into a common, unitless scale while preserving the direction and relative magnitude of preference among alternatives (Equation 1). For each of our decision criteria (objectives), ordinal ranks were rescaled to continuous values ranging from 0 (least desirable) to 1 (most desirable) using a linear transformation based on the maximum rank observed among alternatives. Specifically, normalized utility for alternative i under criterion j was calculated as:

$$U_{ij} = \frac{R_{\max} - R_{ij}}{R_{\max} - 1} \quad (1)$$

where R_{ij} is the rank of alternative i for criteria j (with 1 representing the best-performing alternative) and R_{\max} is the maximum rank across all alternatives. Under this formulation, the best-ranked alternative for a given criterion receives a utility value of 1, whereas the worst-ranked alternative receives a utility value of 0, with intermediate ranks scaled proportionally between these bounds. This normalization approach preserves the relative ordering of alternatives while allowing criteria with different original units and scales to be combined in subsequent utility calculations. Because the transformation is monotonic and does not alter rank order, it serves as a mathematical standardization step rather than an additional subjective weighting. The resulting normalized utilities formed the basis for calculating our overall utility scores under both equal-weight and weighted decision scenarios. Utilities were summed across objectives for each alternative, and the resulting totals were then normalized to a 0–1 scale to facilitate comparison and identification of the best-performing management alternative.

Baseline utility scores

Following normalization of relative rankings, we calculated baseline utility scores to summarize the overall performance of each management alternative across all decision criteria under an equal-weight assumption (Equation 2). These baseline utility scores provided a transparent reference scenario in which all objectives were treated as equally important, prior to the introduction of stakeholder- or decision-maker–defined preferences. For each alternative, normalized utilities across criteria were aggregated using an unweighted linear additive model. Specifically, baseline utility for alternative i was calculated as:

$$U_i = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J U_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where U_{ij} represents the normalized utility of alternative i for criterion j and J is the total number of decision criteria. Under this formulation, each criterion contributes equally to the overall utility score, and resulting values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater overall desirability. These baseline utility scores were used to generate an initial ranking of management alternatives and to illustrate relative performance across objectives in the absence of explicit weighting. This step established a neutral benchmark against which weighted utility scenarios were compared and supported transparent discussion of how alternative value judgments influence final rankings.

Weighted utility scores

To incorporate explicit management priorities into the decision analysis, we calculated weighted utility scores by applying criterion-specific weights to the normalized utilities (Equation 3). Weighting allowed us to formally represent the relative importance of decision objectives in the aggregation of utilities, reflecting value judgments of decision-makers rather than empirical measurements (Table 5). We assigned weights based on priorities identified during regularly scheduled DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup sessions. Higher weights were applied to objectives most closely aligned with aviation safety and risk reduction, whereas lower weights were applied to objectives that played more supporting roles in the decision context (Table 5).

Table 5. Decision-criteria (objective) weights applied in the structured decision-making analysis for DTW’s fish-management program, reflecting stakeholder priorities and values.

Decision criteria	Decision weight
Minimize 5-year cost	0.05
Maximize 5-year effectiveness	0.30
Minimize 5-year treatment frequency	0.10
Minimize 5-year implementation difficulty	0.10
Minimize 5-year liability	0.40
Minimize 5-year attractiveness to wildlife	0.05

After applying criterion-specific weights, we calculated weighted utility scores for each management alternative using the linear additive utility model:

$$U_i = \sum_{j=1}^J w_j U_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where U_{ij} is the normalized utility of alternative i for criterion j , w_j is the weight assigned to criterion j , and J is the total number of criteria. Criterion weights were constrained to sum to 1 ($\sum_j w_j = 1$), ensuring that weighted utility scores remained on a 0–1 scale and were directly comparable among alternatives (Equation 3). The resulting weighted utility scores represented a prioritized evaluation of management alternatives under an explicitly stated value structure. Lastly, our weighted utility scores were used to generate final rankings of management alternatives and to evaluate how the inclusion of our decision-maker preferences influenced outcomes relative to the baseline equal-weight scenario.

Results and Discussion

We applied a structured decision-making framework to a long-standing problem at DTW and identified rotenone as the best-performing alternative for managing fish populations and associated wildlife hazards. Under both equal-weight and weighted decision models, rotenone consistently ranked first and produced substantially higher expected utility scores (0.89–0.93)—approximately twice that of most nonchemical alternatives (0.44–0.54) and nearly three times higher than the status quo (0.35–0.44; Figure 2). This strong performance reflected rotenone’s advantages across multiple

objectives, including effectiveness, reduced treatment frequency, liability reduction, and decreased wildlife attraction (Figure 3). Although some lower-ranked alternatives (e.g., electrofishing) exhibited modest variability in relative position between decision models, the overall ranking structure remained stable, indicating that model outcomes were generally robust to weighting assumptions. Importantly, the top-ranked option did not change. Thus, rotenone consistently outperformed all other management approaches across a range of weighting structures, whereas nonchemical alternatives required clearer trade-offs among decision objectives (Figure 2).

After completing our analysis here, the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup removed several management alternatives from operational consideration due to feasibility constraints. Basin renovation and drying emerged as a strong long-term solution; however, the Workgroup concluded that it was unlikely to be implemented in the near term. Converting ponds to fully drainable or underground systems ranked second in our weighted decision analysis (utility score: 0.78), reflecting both its potential to eliminate long-term fish persistence and its recognition as best management practice (Table 1). Nonetheless, high construction costs, engineering complexity, and project timelines extending beyond the five-year decision horizon made near-term implementation improbable under current conditions. Basin renovation therefore remains a preferred long-term strategy that may be important to incorporate into future infrastructure planning.

Similarly, the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup determined that basin drying without structural renovation would be difficult to achieve operationally. Complete drying would require extended drawdown periods, with a high likelihood of residual pooling that could retain pockets of fish, along with substantial cleanup challenges given the current soft, mucky substrate. Further, eliminating larval fish may require several months of complete desiccation, which is not feasible within an active stormwater-management system (personal communication, Justin Bopp, Michigan Department of Natural Resources – Invasive Species Program). Accordingly, this option was removed from operational consideration despite ranking third in our weighted decision analysis (utility score = 0.71). CO₂ treatment also performed moderately well in our analysis (utility score = 0.70), but the Workgroup ultimately removed it from consideration due to feasibility constraints. Reliable winter implementation would require stormwater-system flexibility that is currently limited by the need to retain de-icing chemicals. As a result, CO₂ was not advanced as a practical management option despite its moderate utility ranking. Collectively, these removals by the Workgroup underscore the iterative character of structured decision making, whereby alternatives are refined or dismissed as feasibility constraints and management priorities are more fully understood (Figure 1).

After these alternatives were removed from consideration, most of the remaining options—largely mechanical removal methods commonly suggested by decision makers—had expected utility scores that were only 38–55% as high as rotenone’s (0.35–0.51 vs. 0.93; Figure 2). These results reflected their comparatively weak performance across the decision criteria (Figure 3). Although nonchemical control methods are generally less expensive per treatment and often more publicly acceptable, they rarely achieve eradication when used alone; with the exception of complete dewatering, piscicides are typically required to fully eliminate a target species from a waterbody (Finlayson et al. 2018). Expert elicitation from the Michigan Department of Natural Resources – Fisheries Division (Lake Erie Management Unit; hereafter, MDNR) further emphasized that goldfish reproduce early and prolifically, such that even a 95% annual removal rate via mechanical methods (e.g., netting) could still allow rapid population recovery (personal communication, John Buszkiewicz and Cleyo Harris). Together, these findings highlight the limited long-term effectiveness of mechanical removal as a stand-alone strategy.

Regulatory and biological considerations likewise supported rotenone as the most effective near-term tool for addressing DTW’s fish problem. Both the Michigan Department of Environment, Great Lakes, and Energy (EGLE; Water Quality and Aquatic Nuisance Control Permits Unit) and the Michigan Department of Natural Resources (MDNR) expressed regulatory support for rotenone use at DTW, noting that fish-bearing ponds represent a substantial public-safety and liability concern because they attract hazardous bird species—providing a clear justification for rotenone application. EGLE, the permitting authority, also emphasized that implementation would require alignment among all regulatory partners, including regional MDNR Fisheries Division approval. Independently of the permitting process, Gurney and Creed (2025) modeled rotenone decay dynamics at DTW to assess operational feasibility and found that, under realistic half-life estimates, stormwater could be retained onsite for a reasonable period to allow degradation prior to discharge. These feasibility findings subsequently reassured permitting agencies and contributed to regulatory support for rotenone use at DTW.

Structured decision-making explicitly recognizes uncertainty as an inherent part of natural resource management, and reducing that uncertainty is a central goal of the process (Runge 2011, Gregory et al. 2012, Fuller et al. 2020). In our case, uncertainty was addressed through literature review, expert elicitation, and incorporation of an independent rotenone-feasibility assessment for DTW (Gurney and Creed 2025). Prior to that work, it was unclear whether rotenone could be permitted or applied safely within the DTW stormwater-management system, given regulatory constraints and discharge considerations. The feasibility analysis demonstrated that rotenone decay rates under DTW site conditions were compatible with water-quality standards and operational holding

times (<1 week), and that most PPE requirements would be lifted by approximately two days post-application (once concentrations declined below ~90 ppb). These findings reduced a major source of uncertainty and enabled the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup to confidently evaluate rotenone as a viable management alternative—ending nearly a decade of debate regarding its feasibility. Combined with our structured decision-making analysis, which identified rotenone as the highest-utility alternative, these studies helped resolve the longstanding debate over which management option was best for DTW.

Understanding fish movement and broader system dynamics will be important for long-term management at DTW. Despite initial concerns from the DTW Pond and Fish Management Workgroup, MDNR indicated that upstream movement of goldfish into ponds through discharge pipes is unlikely, particularly during high-volume discharge events. Although movement during lower-flow periods cannot be ruled out, MDNR noted that goldfish behavior suggests such upstream entry is improbable under typical operating conditions. Regardless of the strategy implemented, MDNR emphasized that fish are still likely to recolonize ponds over time through natural processes (e.g., egg transport), although the expected timeline for recolonization remains uncertain. Accordingly, fish management at DTW may be viewed as an iterative, adaptive process in which outcomes are monitored and strategies refined over time—consistent with the principles of DTW’s Wildlife Hazard Management Plan.

Here, we provide a mathematically supported decision rooted in the best available data and expert knowledge to address a long-standing wildlife-hazard challenge at DTW. By combining structured decision making with regulatory input, biological understanding, and operational feasibility, our analysis consistently identified rotenone as the most effective near-term management option, with basin renovation and drying representing the strongest long-term solution when feasible. Although several commonly suggested nonchemical methods demonstrated moderate performance, they were unlikely to achieve lasting reductions in fish abundance or associated wildlife hazards. Taken together, these findings demonstrate the value of structured decision making for transparently integrating science, uncertainty, and management priorities—and for guiding airport wildlife programs toward defensible, risk-relevant actions.

Figure 2. Normalized total utility scores (0–1) by model type for each management alternative considered for the DTW fish-management program. The equal-weight model assigned identical weights to all decision criteria (objectives), whereas the weighted model incorporated differential weights, including greater emphasis on liability and management effectiveness. Under both models, rotenone was the highest-performing management alternative, with basin-drying options ranking second and third under the weighted model.

Figure 3. Heat map showing normalized utility scores (0–1) for each management alternative across the weighted decision criteria (objectives) evaluated for the DTW fish-management program. Rotenone consistently performed strongly across most objectives, whereas other management alternatives showed more variable performance across criteria.

Ethics Statement

This research acknowledges the ethical considerations involved in the management and handling of fish and wildlife at airports. All management activities referenced in this study would be conducted under appropriate permits, including those issued by relevant federal and state agencies. These actions would be carried out in accordance with established legal and ethical guidelines and be aimed at protecting human life and ensuring aviation safety by mitigating the risk of wildlife-aircraft strikes. Our research does not endorse unnecessary harm to fish and wildlife and supports the use of non-lethal methods whenever feasible. Ethical management practices, including habitat modification and deterrence, are emphasized as primary strategies, with direct control considered only as a last resort and in full regulatory compliance.

Data availability

The R code and data used for analyses in this study are available at the GitHub repository: https://github.com/Steven-M-Gurney/Structured_Decision_Making. The repository also contains a supplemental presentation that provides additional context and detail on the fish-management problem at DTW.

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